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<https://www.ijmsbr.com/>

Impact Factor: 6.049

Time Management and Achievement of Academic Performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

The study was designed to examine the relationship between time management and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. To achieve this objective, survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consisted of the nine departments of the institution with a sample size of 90. The study utilized a multi stage (random and purposive sampling techniques). The instrument used for data collection was Time Management and Achievement of Academic Performance Questionnaire (TMAAPQ). The questionnaire was used to obtain information with regards to independent variables. Tables, simple percentage and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient were adopted as analytical tools for this study. Three hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance using tables and Simple percentage to answer the research questions and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to test the hypotheses. The findings revealed that there is positive significant relationship between time management and academic performance of Trinity Polytechnic, uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Keywords: Time management, planning skills, lateness, stress.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The importance of time management in achievement of academic performance in our colleges cannot be ignored. The organizations in this twenty-first century are required to recognize the importance of time management as a source of sustainable competitive advantage. Time management is an important area of concern in individual's private life as well as in organization from top management to operating level supervisors. Effective time management is one of the valuable assets and the only thing which cannot be changed by man. Nothing can be substituted for time spent or lost. Time management is actually self-management. Time is a valuable personal and the scarcest asset, Drucker (2005). However, to have any realistic chance of achieving goals, students need an intentional and strategic plan for spending

their time in a way that aligns with their goals. Studies reveal that almost 50% of first-year college students in the Polytechnics and Universities report difficulty managing their time effectively (HERI 2014). Several studies reveal that most first-year college students are attending classes while working either part-time or full-time (American Association of Community Colleges 2009). Students must take time management skills very seriously and apply the skills in their academic activities in order to be effective and more productive. Having these skills give students the ability to plan ahead and prioritize upcoming assignments and events. Time management is an important skill that keeps students organized and out of procrastination in their pursuit of academic success.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The world over, students in general, have very busy and stressful life because they are attending classes, completing assignments and studying for examinations. They find it difficult to manage their daily routines and lifestyles that are necessary for creating a balance between academics and social activities. Failing to manage their time appropriately may damage their academic effectiveness and performance thereby resulting in stress. Good time management enables individual to work smarter so that he gets more done in less time, even when time is tight and pressures are high. A time management plan turns into an action plan when you preview what you intend to do, review whether you actually did what you intended to do and close the gap between your intentions and actions. In spite of the aforementioned benefits, the researcher observed that time management is faced with a number of challenges which differ in magnitude and complexity from institution to institution and from country to country. Some of these challenges include lack of planning skills, lateness, stress etc. It is against this background that, this study was designed to examine the relationship between time management and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the relationship between time management and academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Specific objectives include to:

- i. examine the relationship between planning skills and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. evaluate the relationship between lateness and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State.
- iii. assess the relationship between stress and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

- i. What has been the relationship between planning skills and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State?
- ii. What is the relationship between lateness and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State?
- iii. Is there a relationship between stress and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

From the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses were formulated for this study:

- i. There is no significant relationship between planning skills and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between lateness and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State.

- iii. There is no significant relationship between stress and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is significant in several ways since it highlights on those challenges faced by the students of Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State as regards time management. Thus, it will serve as a source of instrument to Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, particularly on time management. The study will be of immense benefit as the findings and recommendations will serve as a guide for policy makers in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State when formulating policies on time management and academic performance. The study will also assist Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State to identify the various factors militating against students' achievement of academic performance and highlight the gaps and lapses that exist between time management and achievement of academic performance of students in the Polytechnic. Finally, the information which this study provides will serve as reference materials for the public and researchers, particularly students of higher institutions for further researches in related areas.

2.1 Review of Related Literature

Time management is very important since it may actually affect students' overall performance and achievements. Time management means those behaviors that aim at achieving an effective use of time while performing certain goal-directed activities, Claessens *et al.*, (2017). Time management relates to how individuals manage their time to suit their daily living or to make it flow steadily with their routines. Alghamdi (2018) believes that one must be restricted to a specified period of time to adjust with present and future situations. Time management is believed to play a vital role in improving students' academic performance and achievements in colleges. According to Brigitte, Claessens, *et al.*, (2015), each and every student should have time management ability which includes setting goals & priorities, using time management mechanism and being organized in using time.

Similarly, Macan, *et al.*, (2020) believe that the secret to achieving success in life is effective and efficient managing skills of this all-important resource called time. Accordingly, Sevari and Kandy (2011) posits that time management skills have an impact on student's academic achievement. Laurie & Hellsten, (2012) agree that a good time management skill boosts students' grades and enhances their productivity. Similarly, Kelly (2014) describes time management skills as quite essential to college students and as one of the keys to higher academic achievements. For effectiveness, Alsalmi, (2018) believes that college students must give priorities to some tasks over the others in order to distribute the sufficient time to get the best results. Time is the scarcest resource of the manager and if it is not managed, nothing else can be managed, Alex (2019). According to Goldsmith (2010) planning your time saves you time because it ensures you start off in the right direction. The author believes that once you have accepted the idea that taking time to plan your time will save you time in the long run then you are ready to create a plan for effectively managing time.

2.1.2 Planning Skills

Students' time planning skills can be considered as one of the aspects that can cause them to be successful. A good time management planning skill is vital for students to shine. However, some of the students lack a good time management planning skill, thus they perform poorly and are negatively affected in life. Accordingly, Alsalmi, (2018) opines that the usage of time by students in higher institutions is related to their daily routines and activities. Studies however, show that lack of time planning skills is one of the major causes of poor academic performance among college students, Macan, *et al.*, (2020). A lot of students perform poorly for reasons that relate more to poor time management planning skills than procrastination.

Studies show that some students procrastinate as a psychological strategy to protect their self-esteem. This according to Rhodewalt and Vohs, (2015) is referred to as self-handicapping. The authors explain that students use this strategy often unconsciously to give themselves a handicap or disadvantage. Similarly, Chu & Cho (2015) believe that some college students receive low grades on tests or examinations basically

due to poor or lack of time management planning skills. The authors opine that students could earn high grades and achieve high academic performance in schools if they could manage their time more effectively. The development of planning skills is very important among the college students. This is because these skills are the key to the solution of different types of problems they may face in the schools, Owen (2017). Planning skills are very essential for student's performance on the whole and especially for undergraduates due to high engagement of planning skills in their learning process. Weinstein & Mayer (2016) believe that one of the effective ways to study students' planning skills is to research them within the framework of learning strategies conception. Kostromina (2013) avers that students' planning skills are very crucial for academic performance and efficiency of learning activity in all stages of education.

2.1.3 Lateness

The issue of lateness is not a new phenomenon in Nigerian colleges. Over the years, lateness by college students has become a recurrent issue. Lateness implies a situation where individual arrives after the proper, scheduled or usual time (Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary, 5th ed., 1995). Lauby (2019) views lateness as people or things not showing up on time. Breezes, *et. al.*, (2020) describe lateness as synonymous with tardiness, which they describe as being slow to act or slow to respond, thus not meeting up with proper or usual timing. Peretomode, (2019) describes the effect of lateness as a system of network breakdown, a situation of not meeting up with programme or time. He describes time as the function and determinant of lateness. There are numerous factors that might be responsible for lateness among college students. Ukoshi (2014) opines that going late to bed as a result of watching films or movies could result in waking up late. Ubogu (2014) concurs that some students who have formed the habit of watching late night movies and home videos usually sleep late and probably wake up late.

Furthermore, Oghuvwu (2018) describes engagement in untimely domestic chores as one of the causes of lateness among college students. He explains that these activities are necessary but doing them at a wrong timing is what cause lateness to college students. Dafiaghor (2011) opines that lateness disorganises and causes distraction to the individual and the whole system. Similarly, Ali (2017) avers that lateness inhibits the process of achieving academic performance in colleges. He further posits that lateness could lead to absenteeism and poor academic performance. Chujor (2014) opines that if lateness by college students is allowed to continue, it may have adverse effect on the attainment of academic performance. Van-Breda (2016) stressed that recurrent lateness to school may not only affect the academic performance of students, it could also create serious problems for such individuals in later life if not checked. However, Chujor (2014) asserts that lateness to school can be excused in some cases when the reasons are cogent and beyond the student's control.

2.1.4 Stress

In recent years, there has been increased attention to the relationship between health and learning among college students. Several school's management often observe the negative impact on attendance and academic achievement that result when students are tired, sick, hung over, depressed or worried. Of particular concern is the level of stress that college students report and how stress affects their success. Stress is a collection of physical, mental, and emotional responses that occur when one encounters something new, challenging, dangerous or exciting, Selye (2018). Stress can be experienced as a positive or negative force in one's life. According to Selye, (2018) positive stress can heighten awareness; improve performance and motivation. Negative stress or distress, can impede performance, reduce concentration and motivation, and contribute to poor health Selye, (2018). Stresses are bad or negative when they undermine both our psychological and physical health. However, Students are subjected to different kinds of stresses, such as the pressure of academics with an obligation to succeed, an uncertain future and difficulties of integrating into the system.

Studies indicate that more than 25% of college students are negatively affected by stress, (American College Health Association 2012). According to American College Health Association, (2011) other factors related to stress, such as sleep difficulties, anxiety, depression, relationship difficulties, work, finances, and concern for a troubled friend or family member are among the top health-related academic impediments faced by

college students. Kaplan and Sadock, (2020), believe that an optimal level of stress can enhance learning ability. Niemi and Vainiomaki, (2019) argue that too much stress can cause physical and mental health problems and may affect the academic achievement of students. Researches have shown that academic workload has been one of the major sources of college students' stress. Chiang (2015) propose that school is one of the main sources of stress among students. Such stress comes from too much homework, unsatisfactory academic performance, preparation for tests, lack of interest in a particular subject or course of study.

2.2 Theoretical Review

The relationship between time management and achievement of academic performance is supported by the following theories:

2.2.1 Goal-setting Theory

The goal-setting theory was proposed Locke in 1968. This theory suggests that the individual goals established by a student play an important role in motivating him for superior academic performance. Skills required include the ability of students to engage in time management skills such as short-range planning, medium-range planning and long-range planning. Time and energy will also need to be given to providing relevant performance incentives, managing processes and providing adequate resources. For students to achieve high academic performance in school as their set goal, they must put premium on the use and management of time through various time management skills. Performance is the key multi character factor intended to attain outcomes which has a major connection with planned objectives of the students. Students' goals achievement according to this theory is achievement of academic performance through proper time management skills.

2.2.2 Expectancy Theory

Expectancy theory, developed by Victor Harold Vroom in 1964 is based on three perceptions: *expectancy*, *instrumentality*, and *valence*, which, by themselves, can influence an individual's motivation and achievement of goal. Expectancy theory is originated from the belief that one's effort should correspond with the desired performance. Instrumentality is the belief that if the performance expectation is met, the reward will be received, and Valence refers to the value the individual places on the reward. According to the first perception of expectancy, if students do not believe that good time management skills will be rewarded for high performance, they may be less likely to value the time. Providing clear descriptions of the knowledge and skills that will be rewarded, providing opportunities to acquire and apply the knowledge and skills, and the presence of support and technical assistance, are all things that can positively influence the expectancy perception. Instrumentality, which refers to how strongly a person perceives a connection to be between achieving a goal and to experiencing a positive outcome holds that if students achieve their desired results as a result of good time management skills, they will place premium on time management. If they do not believe the results are obtainable as a reward of proper time management skills, they are not likely to be motivated to make a good use of time. This is one of the reasons why the system to measure performance must be both valid and reliable and take into account all of the factors that influence students' achievement. Instrumentality also has a direct relationship on valence, the final perception. Valence in this context refers to value. This refers to whether students value the rewards associated with obtaining the desired goals. Using expectancy theory as a base for this study will explore students' attitude and perception of reward for time management skills. It will also identify key attributes of effective time management skills.

2.3 Empirical Review

Time management has received great attention from many organisations over time now. However, this section would look at the previous studies on time management and achievement of academic performance in colleges. A study by Arahimi & Mardini (2014) on the impact of management time on academic performance. The population of the study comprised 300 students. The finding revealed that there is a relationship between planning and academic performance. Cemaloglu & Filiz (2008) conducted a study which aimed at studying the relationship between academic performance and time management skills in

Education College at Ghazi University in Turkey. The study results showed that showed the existence of significant positive relationship between planning time and academic performance of students. Abusakour (2003) carried out a study on the obstacles of time management in the West Bank, Palestine The study adopted descriptive approach in collection of data. The finding showed that the obstacles of time management relate directly to the obstacles in planning. Abulshawi and Abusultana (2003) conducted a study on time management in Yarmouk University. The study results showed that there is a positive correlation between time management skill and achievement of academic performance. Onoyase (2013) conducted a study investigating lateness as a recurrent problem among secondary school students in Akoko South East Local Government Area of Ondo State. The findings showed that there is positive significant relationship between lateness and achievement of academic performance. Veena, *et. al.*, (2016) carried out a study to identify the sources of stress among students of high and low academic performance. The questionnaire was administered on 656 pure sciences and applied science under graduate students from Bangalore City. The findings revealed that, there is a relationship between stress and students' academic performance.

Harlina. et al (2014) conducted a study on stress and stressors. The findings of the study showed that, there is a significant relationship between stress and academic performance. Karen (2012) carried out a research on the impact of stress on the academic performance of Hispanic undergraduate students with the aim of identifying stressors that have a negative impact on academic performance of Hispanic undergraduate students. The findings of the study revealed that, there is a significant relationship between stress and academic performance. Mussarat, *et. al.*, (2013) conducted a study to explore the effect of academic stress on students' performance with a population of 150. The results showed that there is an effect of academic stress on student's performance.

3. Methodology

This chapter is concerned with the methodology used in achieving the objectives of the study. It covers research design, study area, population of the study, sample size and sampling technique, sources of data collection, instrument for data collection, validity of research instrument, reliability of the instrument, administration of the instrument, method of data analysis and decision rule.

3.1 Research Design

The historical/descriptive and survey methods are adopted for this study. It enabled the researcher to elicit information from a sub-set of the entire population to guide the study. Descriptive method is the situation analysis of an event while the survey design involves the collection and analysis of data from sampled population from the field leading to inferences. A combination of these methods was considered appropriate for the study because it is intended to lead us to empirical findings and generalization.

3.2 The Study Area

This study was conducted in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The choice of this study area was informed by their involvement in academic activities/programmes.

3.3 Population and Sample Size

The population from which inferences were drawn and generalization made were the entire students of Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. A total sample size of ninety (90) students drawn from the nine departments was used in this study. Ten (10) selected students in each of the nine departments were relevant in the study. Questionnaire was administered to each of them and their responses used in the final analysis.

3.4 Sampling Technique

The study adopted multi-stage (purposive and random) sampling techniques. The main goal of purposive sampling is to focus on particular characteristics of a population that are of interest to the researcher or have certain characteristics relevant to the study. The essence of using the purposive sampling technique stems from the fact that all the elements in the population of the study would be relevant to the study. The researcher also adopted random method in the sense that students were randomly selected and questionnaire issued to them for response.

3.5 Sources of Data Collection

Data were collected from primary and secondary sources. Primary data were obtained through questionnaire and personal interviews with the staff and students of the Polytechnic. This method was adopted to enable detailed and independent information not covered by the questionnaire to be expressed by the respondents. Secondary data were obtained from published reports, books, internet, journals, newspapers and magazines.

3.6 Instrument for Data Collection

Data were collected through questionnaire titled “Time Management and Achievement of Academic Performance Questionnaire (TMAAPQ)” carefully designed and administered to the respondents, as well as through personal interviews. On the whole, the questionnaire constituted the major instrument for data collection. The questionnaire contains sections A and B. Section A contains personal information about the respondents. Section B is the main body of the questionnaire. This section contains sixteen (16) close ended questions using a four-point scale instrument through which the opinions of the respondents were expressed. Their responses were measured by means of a four-category rating system as follows:

SA	-	Strongly agree	4
A	-	Agree	3
D	-	Disagree	2
SD	-	Strongly disagree	1

3.7 Validity of Research Instrument

The validity of the research instrument was assessed by the research’s supervisor and other research experts in the School of Management Sciences of the Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. These experts assessed the relevance of each item in relation to the objectives of the study, the hypotheses to be tested and language used in developing the items as well as the comprehensibility of each item in relation to the cognitive level of the respondents. They validated the instrument by effecting necessary corrections, examining the contents and ascertaining clarification of ideas as well as appropriateness of the items. The final instrument is reflected on the appendix.

3.8 Reliability of the Instrument

Reliability in this context refers to the measure of consistency of the instrument used in eliciting relevant and desirable responses from respondents so that the objectives can be reliably and meaningfully achieved. In order to determine the reliability of the instrument used in the study, the corrected questionnaire was administered randomly on selected students of Sure Foundation Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. This approach was repeated with the same group after one-week period and the results obtained from the first and second pre-test were consistent, therefore, the instrument is reliable.

3.9 Administration of the Instrument

The questionnaires were personally administered by the researcher to the respondents during official hours at school. The exercise was done with the help of heads of department of each school of the polytechnic.

3.10 Method of Data Analysis

Data retrieved for the study were analyzed with tables and simple percentages. For the purpose of testing the hypotheses, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was adopted to test the three hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

4. Data Presentation And Analysis

This chapter deals with the presentation, description and analysis of data collected from the sample under study. The results represent the answers by the respondents to items in the questionnaire. Data obtained from respondents are presented in tabular form and analyzed accordingly. It is also in this chapter that the hypotheses earlier formulated in this study are tested. The questionnaire was completed by the 60 eligible respondents. This form the basis for analysis.

4.1 Analysis of Demographic Data

Table 4.1: Demographic Distribution of Respondents (N= 60)

Item	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	20	41.2
	Female	40	58.8
Age	25-30years	22	32.4
	31 – 35years	24	35.3
	36– 40years	10	23.5
	41years and above	4	8.8
Work Status	Junior staff	46	67.6
	Senior staff	14	20.6
	Management staff	8	11.8
Highest Academic Qualification	OND/NCE	16	23.5
	HND/BSC	49	72.1
	M.SC/MBA	3	4.4
Work Experience	1-2 years	27	39.7
	3 – 5years	32	47.1
	6-10years	6	8.8
	11 and above	3	4.4

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

The result in Table 4.1 shows the demographic profile of respondents. In terms of gender, male respondents constituted 41.2% of participants while 58.8% were female. Result also shows that majority of respondents (35.3%) were between ages 31 – 35, and a little more than half of respondents were junior employees (67.6%). Table 4.1 also shows that the highest number of respondents (49) was first degree holders and about 47.1% had work experiences of 3-5years. The demographic characteristics of respondents under survey seem to suggest that the study was conducted among appropriate population category.

4.2 Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis one

There is no significant relationship between planning skills and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State.

This hypothesis was analysed using the Pearson product moment correlation analysis and the results are as summarized on Table 4.2

Table 4.2: Relationship between planning skills and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

		Planning skills	Achievement of academic performance
Planning skills	Pearson Correlation	1	.656**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	60	60
Achievement of academic performance	Pearson Correlation	.656**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2022

It can be observed from Table 4.2 that relationship between planning skills and academic performance is positive and significant at 0.01 level ($r = 0.656$, $p < 0.01$). Hence, the null hypothesis one is rejected with a conclusion that significant relationship exists planning skills and academic performance. This may suggest that academic performance of the institution in terms of excellent examination results, and better course accreditation, and responsive organisation to the community. Thus, the effective the planning skills, the better improved the academic's performance of the polytechnics.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between lateness and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.3: Relationship between lateness and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

		Lateness	Academic Performance
Lateness	Pearson Correlation	1	.795**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	60	60
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	.795**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

In Table 4.3, result shows that relationship between lateness and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnics is positive and significant at 0.01 probability level ($r = 0.795$, $p < 0.01$). Hence, null hypothesis two is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant relationship between lateness and achievement of academic performance. This may imply that improved academic performance of the organisation under survey could be affected by lateness. Thus, when the school encourages punctuality, the better the achievement of its academic performance.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant relationship between stress management and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.4: Relationship between stress management and achievement of academic performance.

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

		Stress Management	Academic Performance
Stress Management	Pearson Correlation	1	.666**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	60	60
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	.666**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	60	60

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

The results in Table 4.4 illustrate that stress management ($r = 0.66$, $p < 0.01$) is significantly related to academic performance. Therefore, null hypothesis three is rejected with a conclusion that there is significant relationship between stress management and academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic. This means that Trinity Polytechnics can improve its academic performance by implementing effective stress management initiatives.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The main aim of this study was to examine the relationship between time management and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. This section is however, concerned with the discussion of findings that emerged from the result of data analysis. They are discussed under specific objectives of the study.

4.4.1 Relationship between Planning Skills and Achievement of Academic Performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

The first objective was to examine the relationship between planning skills and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Pearson correlation analysis was performed with a view towards achieving the above objective. It was observed that, relationship between planning skills and academic performance is positive and significant at 0.01 level ($r = 0.656$, $p < 0.01$). Hence, the null hypothesis one is rejected with a conclusion that significant relationship exists between planning skills and academic performance. This may suggest academic performance of the institution in terms of excellent examination results, and better course accreditation, and responsive organisation to the community. Thus, the effective the planning skills, the better and improved the academic performance of the polytechnic. This finding is consistent with Macan, *et. al.*, (2020) who believe that lack of time planning skills is one of the major causes of poor academic performance among college students.

4.4.2 Relationship between Lateness and Achievement of Academic Performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

The second objective attempted to examine whether significant relationship exists between lateness and academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. It was revealed that relationship between lateness and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnics is positive and significant at 0.01 probability level ($r = 0.795$, $p < 0.01$). Hence, null hypothesis two is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant relationship between lateness and achievement of academic performance. This may imply that improved academic performance of the organisation under survey could be affected by lateness. Thus, when the school encourages punctuality, the better the achievement of its academic performance. This finding is in line with Chujor (2014) who opined that if lateness by college students is allowed to continue, it may have adverse effect on the attainment of academic performance. The finding is also supported by Van-Breda (2016) who stressed that recurrent lateness to school may not only affect the academic performance of students, it could also create serious problems for such individuals in later life if not checked.

4.4.3 Relationship between Stress and Achievement of Academic Performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

The third objective attempted to examine whether significant relationship exists between stress and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The result showed that stress management ($r = 0.66$, $p < 0.01$) is significantly related to academic performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis three is rejected with a conclusion that there is significant relationship between stress management and academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic. This means that Trinity Polytechnics can improve its academic performance by implementing effective stress management initiatives. This finding is in support with Niemi and Vainiomaki, (2019) who argued that too much stress can cause physical and mental health problems and may affect the academic achievement of students.

5. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary of the Findings

This research was designed to examine the relationship between time management and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. To achieve this objective, survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consisted of all the nine departments of the institution with sample size 90. The study utilised multi stage (purposive and random sampling techniques). The instrument used for data collection was Time Management and Achievement of Academic Performance Questionnaire (TMAAPQ). Tables, simple percentage and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient were adopted as analytical tools for this study. Three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study showed that there was a positive significant relationship between time management and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The result of the findings also revealed academic performance of the institution in terms of excellent examination results, and better course accreditation, and responsive organisation to the

community. Thus, the effective the planning skills, the better and improved the academic performance of the polytechnic.

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, there is a significant relationship between time management and achievement of academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The independent variables namely; planning skills, lateness and stress contribute significantly to academic performance. The findings revealed academic performance of the institution in terms of excellent examination results, and better course accreditation, and responsive organisation to the community. Thus, the effective the planning skills, the better and improved the academic performance of the polytechnic. From the findings of this study, it could be concluded that the inability of most Polytechnics to achieve academic performance or objectives may be attributed to external or exogenous factors which are outside the control of the organisations.

5.3 Recommendations

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Polytechnics, particularly, Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State should be more time management effective in order to ensure improved academic performance of the institution.
- ii. The students and staff of the Polytechnic should be unevenly and fairly evaluated and rewarded to ensure accurate academic performance achievement.
- iii. The internal and external environment of the institution should be taken into consideration when formulating decisions on academic performance.
- iv. The Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State should introduce a sound reward system for outstanding performances so as to motivate both the students and staff of the institution.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Studies

The following areas are suggested for further researches.

- i. Same study should be carried out in other Polytechnics in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. Same study should be replicated in College of Education, Akwa Ibom State.
- iii. Same study should be replicated in University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

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APPENDIX I

SECTION A

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Please kindly tick where appropriate in the spaces provided below:

1. Gender: Male [] Female []
2. Age: 15-20 [] 21-30 [] 31-40 [] 41 and above []
3. Marital Status: Single [] Married [] Divorced [] Widowed []
4. Highest Educational Qualification: SSCE [] OND/NCE [] HND/B.Sc. [] M.Sc./MBA [] Ph.D. []
5. Years of Service/Experience: 0 – 2 [] 3 – 5 [] 6 – 10 [] 11 and above []
6. Rank: Management Staff [] Senior Staff [] Junior Staff []

SECTION B

S/N		SA	A	SD	D
A	TIME PLANNING SKILLS DIMENSION				
7	Your Polytechnic planning skill programme is effective.				
8	Your Polytechnic lecture timetable is considerable				
9	Your Polytechnic planning programmes is in line with the NBTE requirement.				
10	Students in your Polytechnic record low performance due to procrastination.				
B	LATENESS DIMENSION				
12	Students in your Polytechnic always record timely achievements.				
13	Students in your Polytechnic always meet assignments submission deadlines.				
14	A lot of students in your Polytechnic engage in late night activities.				
15	Your Polytechnic students are fond of watching late night movies.				
C	STRESS DIMENSION				
16	Your Polytechnic has a balanced academic work load.				
17	Students in your polytechnic are always felt worried and intimidated.				
18	A lot of your Polytechnic students lack interest in certain courses.				
19	Your Polytechnic students always complain of unsatisfactory results.				
D	ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE DIMENSION				
20	Your Polytechnic examination' results is excellent.				
21	Your Polytechnic records a good number of distinctions annually.				
22	The rate of failure in your Polytechnic is low.				
23	Your Polytechnic is known to be responsive to NBTE regulations.				